

Reaction between Potassium Oxalate and Iodine and the Relation between Intensity and Velocity.

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Dhar (*Proc. K. Akad. Wetensch. Amstardam*, 1916, **18**, 1084) was the first to investigate kinetics of the reaction between potassium oxalate and iodine in light as well as in dark and he observed that the velocity of the reaction is greatly accelerated by light and is greater in sunlight than in diffused light. Later on Berthoud and Bellenot (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1924, **7**, 307) investigated the same reaction and found it to be proportional to the square root of the incident radiation and this conclusion is supported by Briers, Chapman and Walters (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 562). Mukherji and Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, **32**, 1308) observed that the reactions between potassium oxalate and iodine, and ammonium oxalate and iodine are proportional to the square root of the incident radiation in presence of white light obtained from 1000 watt gas filled tungsten filament lamp and also of radiation of wave-length 4725Å. Recently Bhattacharya and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **6**, 475) have investigated the same reaction in radiations of wave-lengths 5650Å and 7904Å using different intensities. They have used potassium iodide and free iodine.

The author has also studied this reaction in dark and in light of various wave-lengths and established the relation between intensity and velocity for this photochemical reaction in various regions. The results are tabulated below.

Dark reaction.

$I_2 = 0.00258M$. $KI = 0.2806M$. $K_2C_2O_4 = 0.7595M$. Temp. = 28°.

t.	Thiosulphate required.	$K_1 = 1/t \times \log a/a-x$.
0 min.	9.1 c.c.	—
1125	7.7	0.0000644
3900	5.1	0.0000644

Mean $K_1 = 0.0000644$

K_1 calculated as $k_{\frac{1}{2}} = 0.000440$.

Temperature coefficient of the dark reaction.

Temp.	K_1 .	Temp. coeff. $K_1(38^\circ)/K_1(28^\circ)$.
28°	0·0000644	—
38°	0·000442	6·86

Also $K_2 = K_1 E/R \left(\frac{T_2 - T_1}{T_1 T_2} \right)$. Therefore $E = 36240$ Calories. K_1 at 38° calculated as $k_{\frac{1}{2}} = 0·00302$.

Relation between intensity and velocity.

(1) *Source* = total light from 1000 watt lamp. Temp. = 28°.

Diameter of the aperture = 2cm.

t .	Thiosulphate required.	$k_{\frac{1}{2}} = 2/t (\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{a-x})$.
0 min.	10·2 c.c.	—
10	8·4	0·058
21	6·6	0·059
33	4·9	0·059
		————— $K_{\frac{1}{2}} \text{ mean} = 0·0586$
Diameter of the aperture.	$k_{\frac{1}{2}} = 2/t (\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{a-x})$.	Purely photochemical $k_{\frac{1}{2}}$.
2 cm.	0·059	0·05836
1"	0·040	0·03956
0·5"	0·0285	0·0280
Ratio of intensities.	Ratio of velocities.	Ratio of $\sqrt{\text{Intensities}}$.
$(2/1)^2 = 4$	$\frac{0·05856}{0·03956} = 1·48$	2
$(1/0·5)^2 = 4$	$\frac{0·03956}{0·0280} = 1·41$	2
$(2/0·5)^2 = 16$	$\frac{0·05856}{0·0280} = 2·09$	4

REACTION BETWEEN POTASSIUM OXALATE AND IODINE 651

Temp. = 38°.

Diameter of the aperture.	$k_{\frac{1}{2}} = 2/t (\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{a-x})$.	Purely photochemical $k_{\frac{1}{2}}$.
2 cm.	0.202	0.199
1"	0.1350	0.132
0.5"	0.0862	0.0832.

Ratio of intensities.	Ratio of velocities.	Ratio of $\sqrt{\text{Intensities}}$.
$(2/1)^2 = 4$	$\frac{0.199}{0.132} = 1.50$	2
$(1/0.5)^2 = 4$	$\frac{0.132}{0.0832} = 1.58$	2
$(2/0.5)^2 = 16$	$\frac{0.199}{0.0832} = 2.4$	4

Temperature coefficient of the reaction in total light.

Diameter of the aperture.	$k_{\frac{1}{2}}$ at 28°.	$k_{\frac{1}{2}}$ at 38°.	Temp. coeff. $K_{\frac{1}{2}}(38^\circ)/K_{\frac{1}{2}}(28^\circ)$.
2 cm.	0.0585	0.199	3.4
1 cm.	0.0395	0.132	3.4

(2) Source = 5750 Å

Light filter—nitrosodimethylaniline + Ni(NO₃)₂ 2.08M each in 1 cm. cell. Range of transmission=5200—6300 Å. Mean $\lambda = 5750\text{Å}$. Maximum % T = 0.10 (Bhagwat and Dhar, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 35, 2401). Diameter of the aperture=2 cm. Temp.=38°.

t.	Thiosulphate required.	$k_{\frac{1}{2}} = 2/t(\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{a-x})$.
0 min.	10.6 c.c.	—
10	9.6	0.0305
20	8.6	0.0305
40	7.0	0.0305

Mean $k_{\frac{1}{2}} = 0.0305$

Diameter of the aperture.	$k_{\frac{1}{2}} = 2/t (\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{a-x})$.	Purely photochemical $k_{\frac{1}{2}}$.
2 cm.	0.0305	0.0275
1	0.0160	0.0130
Ratio of intensities.	Ratio of velocities.	Ratio of $\sqrt{\text{intensities}}$.
$(2/1)^2 = 4$	$\frac{0.0275}{0.0130} = 2.11$	2

(3) Source = 6700 Å.

Light filter—methyl violet 0.100 g. in 100 c. c. + K_2CrO_4 5.5882N. Normal solution being expressed as $\frac{K_2CrO_4}{2}$; each in 1 cm. cell. Range of transmission = 6280-7200 Å. Maximum % $T = 56$ (Bhagwat and Dhar, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 35, 2391). Temp. = 38°

Diameter of the aperture.	$k_{\frac{1}{2}} = 2/t (\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{a-x})$.	Purely photochemical $k_{\frac{1}{2}}$.
2 cm.	0.0433	0.0403
1	0.0232	0.0202
Ratio of intensities.	Ratio of velocities.	Ratio of $\sqrt{\text{intensities}}$.
$(2/1)^2 = 4$	$\frac{0.0403}{0.0202} = 2.0$	$\sqrt{4} = 2$

(4) Source = 8500 Å infra red.

Light filter— $K_2Cr_2O_7$ 0.513 M in 1 cm. cell + 4 cobalt glasses (Bhagwat and Dhar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 911). Temp. = 38°.

Diameter of the aperture.	$k_{\frac{1}{2}} = 2/t (\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{a-x})$.	Purely photochemical $k_{\frac{1}{2}}$.
2 cm.	0.0186	0.0156
1	0.00987	0.00687
Ratio of intensities.	Ratio of velocities.	Ratio of $\sqrt{\text{intensities}}$.
$(2/1)^2 = 4$	$\frac{0.0156}{0.00687} = 2.27$	2

REACTION BETWEEN POTASSIUM OXALATE AND IODINE 653

The results of the relation between intensity and velocity are summarised in the following table.

Source.	Range of transmission.	Ratio of intensities.	Ratio of $\sqrt{\text{intensities}}$	Ratio of velocities.
1000 watt lamp	...	$(2/1)^2 = 4$	2	1.48
..	...	$(1/0.5)^2 = 4$	2	1.41
..	...	$(2/0.5)^2 = 16$	4	2.09
5750Å	5200-6300Å	$(2/1)^2 = 4$	2	2.0
6700Å	6280-7200Å	$(2/1)^2 = 4$	2	2.11
8500Å	...	$(2/1)^2 = 4$	2	2.27

The table clearly shows that the relation between intensity and velocity is not constant but as the velocity of the reaction decreases, the relation steadily rises from less-than under-root to under-root. Usually photochemical acceleration falls with increasing wave-length but in case of nitrosodimethylaniline and K_2CrO_4 as light filters, because the intensity of the transmitted light is very low, maximum being only 0.1 %, the velocity constant is less than that of 6280-7200 Å and consequently the ratio of intensity and velocity is higher.

Berthoud and Bellenot (*loc. cit.*) observed the temperature coefficient for 10° between 25° and 40° to be 3.22 and 3.15 in red and blue light respectively. Berthoud (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1931, 27, 484) has repeated his experiments and observed that his results do not agree with his previous work and also with that of Dhar (*loc. cit.*).

My results of the dark temperature coefficient and the value of E calculated shows that Dhar's results are quite reproducible. Very recently Young and Style have investigated the same reaction (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1931, 27, 493) and claim to have confirmed the results of Berthoud and Bellenot (*loc. cit.*) and have observed that the value is at minimum in the neighbourhood of $579 \mu\mu$. In view of Berthoud's observations these values seem to be doubtful. Moreover, the extinction for this reaction increases as the wave-length falls. It is usually observed that as the frequency of the incident radiation increases, the temperature coefficient falls. Hence Young and Styles' observations must be taken with caution,

According to Bhattacharya and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 4, 197, 493), the relation between intensity and velocity can show a relationship which is less than or greater than the direct, depending on the amount of acceleration. The present author (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1931, 199, 412 ; *U. P. Acad. Sci.*, 1931, 1, 54) has deduced a theoretical expression connecting velocity with intensity and has shown that this relationship can never exceed the direct. This view is borne out by the above results.

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